

pyteeasc - A Python Toolbox for Automated Parameter Variations in AspenPlus

pyteeasc is a Python toolbox for performing automated parameter variation studies on Aspen Plus® simulations. It leverages `aspenparserDLR` for reliable data exchange between Python and Aspen Plus and integrates `pyteeauc` for consistent unit handling and conversion, ensuring physically correct model interactions.

The toolbox enables users to systematically vary model parameters over defined ranges, execute large sets of simulation runs, and collect structured results for further analysis. By allowing the integration of custom Python scripts into the workflow, the tool extends standard Aspen-based modeling toward flexible, programmable, and data-driven process studies.

Key Features

- Automated parameter variation
 - Definition of model parameters and their variation ranges
 - Execution of batch simulation runs with structured result collection
- Robust Aspen–Python coupling
 - Data transfer into and out of Aspen Plus via `aspenparserDLR`
 - Consistent unit handling and conversion using `pyteeauc`
- Extensible modeling workflow
 - Integration of user-defined Python scripts during parameter studies
 - Custom logic and calculations can be executed alongside simulation runs
- Multi-flowsheet coupling
 - Linking of two independent Aspen Plus simulations
 - Definition of an outgoing stream from one model as the incoming stream of another
- Lookup table generation and reuse
 - Execution of parameter studies to generate surrogate lookup tables
 - Integration of precomputed results into Aspen models to reduce computational effort

Requirements

The tool requires the two in-house repositories `aspenparserDLR`, and `pyteeauc`. Their required version together with additionally required publicly available libraries are listed below.

```
dependencies = [  
    "aspenparserDLR @ git+https://.../aspenparserdlr.git@0.2.13",
```

```
"pyteeauc @ git+https://.../pyteeauc.git@0.1.2",
"loguru>=0.6.0",
"pandas>=2.0.1",
"pydantic==2.6.2",
"pywin32>=304",
"PyYAML>=6.0",
"scipy>=1.11.1",
"tinydb>=4.7.1"
]
requires-python = ">=3.10"
```

Usages

Parameter variation study

The automated parameter variation study requires the preparation of a few configuration files such as:

1. Included Simulation Objects (Simulation Files / LookUpObjects)
2. Process Variation Parameters
3. Record Options (same as for aspenparserDLR)
4. Optional: Additional Python scripts

Definition of included simulation objects:

```
config_type: SimulationControl
config_version: 0.8
date: 06.05.2024
simulation_control_setup:
  name: example_run
  multiple_data_sources:
    active: false
  result_path: result_files
  run_options:
    single_run: false
    variation_run:
      active: true
  object_list:
    syngas_train:
      type: AspenObject
      simulation_path: path\to\simulation\file.bkp
      process_vars: path\to\process\variables.yaml
      record_options: record_options.yaml
      additional_features:
        additional_script:
```

```
config_path: additional_script_config.yaml
active: true
```

Process Parameter Definition

The list of process vars is defined as follows:

```
config_type: ProcessVars
config_version: 0.7
date: 26.09.2023
process_vars:
  - var_name: temp_reactor
    active: true
    info: Setting the temperature of a reactor
    access_mode: w
    vars:
      - obj_name: REACTOR
        path: B_TEMP
        hierarchy: []
        value_init: 150
        value_vars:
          - 150
          - 180
```

Record Options

Can be seen here: [aspenparserDLR](#)

Additional Feature

The additional features are implemented by pointing to the script and its function defined in a yaml file as well. There is also the option of including it only in dependence on a certain process variable's value. Furthermore, settings can be defined in the YAML file which will be made available through the initialization procedure and might be used within the function itself.

```
config_type: AdditionalFeature
info: Simple description of the additional feature
modules: # Defining which modules in which files are supposed
         to be executed.
  - file: ..\add_feature_file.py
    module: add_feature_function_to_be_called
primary: # Defining when this additional feature is supposed
        to be included.
  - ptype: process_var
    name: var1
    values:
      - 2
setting_val: 1
```

```
other_input: 0.5
```

```
...
```

Variation run output

- variation run
 - var_run_id
 - first_single_run_id
 - blocks
 - Compr.csv
 - Flash2.csv
 - ...
 - streams
 - MATERIAL.csv
 - HEAT.csv
 - WORK.csv
 - hcurves
 - HEATER1.csv
 - ...
 - next_single_run_id
 - ...
 - ...

Execute parameter run

To execute the parameter study, the SimObject has to be initialized by providing the path to its main configuration file. Subsequently, the object's functions can be triggered to run single runs or a full parameter run.

```
from pathlib import Path
from pyteeasc import sc_object as sco

path_to_sc_config = Path('path/to/configuration_file.yaml')
sc_obj = sco.create_sim_control(path_to_sc_config)

sc_obj.run_simulation()
sc_obj.closing_simulation()
```

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